

ENHANCING STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE OF ENGLISH SPEAKING FLUENCY: THE ROLE OF PRONUNCIATION, CONTEXT OF SITUATION AND LANGUAGE FEATURES

Pham Huu Duc

International University – Vietnam National University HCMC

Email: phduc@hcmiu.edu.vn

ABSTRACT

Speaking fluent English has always been difficult for students of English as a foreign language (EFL students). There have been a lot of studies about how to help language learners overcome this difficulty. This paper aimed at presenting the methodology of teaching students how to display fluent performance of speaking English through the survey investigation of intermediate level students and through the analysis of relationship between pronunciation, context of situation and language features to provide solution to students' problems in oral communication. The results were that the performance of a speaking activity which involved producing the correctness of sounds, grammatical accuracy, and control of the content showed that learners could improve their language competency. This study could be also undertaken as a basis for helping language learners speak naturally and hopefully for helping learners perform at a level above their normal level of performance.

Key words: Context of situation, fluency, language features, pronunciation, speaking skill

1 INTRODUCTION

Speaking English is considered difficult for EFL students since it is a productive skill that requires a lot of effort. Therefore, it is difficult to acquire this skill compared with other skills. The speaker's brain must carry out many functions simultaneously such as getting the appropriate ideas, using vocabulary and grammatical structures correctly, and at the same time, getting the vocal cords to sound to convey the message to the audience. Besides, some problems that students have to encounter contribute to difficulty in their speaking English such as the lack of linguistic knowledge, and inactive participation in communication. Students often have difficulty expressing their opinions during speaking classes or in their communication with their teachers. They often mispronounce the final sounds, thus making themselves misunderstood. Students often find it hard to communicate their ideas with their lecturers and classmates when they attend the lectures and work in groups. The study aimed at helping EFL university students to perform speaking fluently through identifying the problems that students often have such as pronunciation, context of situation and language features, finding out the causes of the problems and working out the solutions to these problems in order to teach students how to communicate

more effectively. The study may methodologically contribute to solving potential problems for intermediate level students in oral communication at higher levels.

2 Literature review

This literature review is limited to the questions concerning students' problems in performing speaking tasks. Most speaking literature provides program and instructional technique description; still, this review addresses the works of some authors in teaching speaking skill in association with the explanation of a linguistic perspective. Though much research on teaching speaking skill has been carried out, evaluative studies using qualitative methods to measure the effectiveness of the study are comparatively scarce.

2.1 The role of pronunciation in teaching speaking skill

Pronunciation plays an important role in speaking English. Pronouncing English correctly will help students improve both speaking and listening and ensure that they are easily understood by both non-native and native speakers; thus, this leads to effective verbal communication. However, according to Morley (1991: 481-520), it is necessary to combine pronunciation with oral communication, emphasizing on individual learners' needs and task-based practices and developing teaching methodologies. Pronouncing intelligible is essential in communication competence and this must be included in teaching and learning speaking and students are expected to do it well; yet teaching phonemes hardly contributes to the understanding in communication (Castillo, 1991). Therefore, teaching pronunciation should not focus on the acquisition of perfect pronunciation, but on the development of intelligibility and communicability (Morley, 1991: 500).

2.2 Context of situation in teaching speaking skill

Although pronunciation plays a great part in speaking, there are still other factors that contribute to conveying messages successfully to audience. Bailey and Savage (1994) viewed speaking as the most demanding of the four skills, because when attempting to speak, learners had to muster their thought and encode those ideas in the vocabulary and syntactic structures of the target language. Ur (1996: 121) identified the problems that resulted in preventing students from speaking English, saying that speaking skill was intuitively the most important compared with other three skills (listening, reading and writing). She also pointed out that some of the problems with speaking skills were "inhibition, nothing to say, low participation, and mother-tongue use". Ur has paved the way for the innovation in the teaching methods.

Richards & Rodgers (2014) indicated that the speaking elements for the teaching and learning cycle concerning speaking skill included: 1) Context elements (Topic: where people come from; Text-type: a description or a conversation; Context of situation: field – place, tenor – learner to classmates, teacher, friends, etc., mode – spoken project), 2) Language elements (vocabulary sets relating to the subject, use of joining words, attitude words, personal pronouns, organization of information, simple clauses, noun groups, verbs, circumstances of place, strategies for managing the spoken process, speaking strategies, speaking practice, and ideas for effective presentation).

Not all the teaching methods are good therapies to treat speaking problems. Some researchers have gone as far as the systemic functional linguistics when they try to apply the theory in dealing with problems that occur in speaking. Feez and Joyce (1998), based on the work by Halliday (2004), Martin 1992), and Suzanne (1993) introduced the way to work out the text-based syllabus design in which they mentioned the method to teach speaking in the perspective of the systemic functional linguists. The theory mentions three meta-functions (ideational, interpersonal, and textual) and three aspects of the context of situation (field, tenor, and mode) as the basis on which the performance of language is built. Ideational, interpersonal, and textual are the aspects of discourse semantics; and field, tenor, and mode describe the context of the situation. Feez and Joyce found out a way to teaching speaking in the view of systemic functional linguistics.

2.3 Language features in teaching speaking skill

According to Feez and Joyce (1998), language features in teaching a speaking activity are presented at three levels: text level, clause level and expression level. Text level consists of interaction strategies involved with opening and closing a conversation, confirming and clarifying, asking for repetition, challenging content and personal demands, requesting and responding. At clause level, WH-questions and interrogatives and requests (modals, question tags, embedded clauses are used with vocabulary related to qualifications and experience. At expression level, intonation (related to WH-questions, interrogatives and requests) and strategies (for self-correction and repair for mispronunciation) are used.

2.4 Relationship between pronunciation, context of situation and language features

According to Eggins (1993:76), phonology is represented as the realization of the context of situation. The three significant situational variables are field (what is talked about?), mode (what form the message takes?) and tenor (who is spoken to?). The discourse semantics is closely related to the language features. The relationship is displayed as follows (Figure 1).

Although much work relating to improving students' pronunciation and verbal communication in English has been done so far, more studies need to be conducted to give a satisfactory explanation to students' problems in speaking and work as the basis on which the teaching methods are constructed. This study dealt with the problems that intermediate level students encounter in their pronunciation of final consonant sounds and their speaking in specific contexts together with the exploring language features.

Figure 1: Relationship between pronunciation, context of situation and language features

(Source: Eggins, 1993:77)

3 THE METHODOLOGY

The research uses the descriptive method, statistics, and qualitative method (using a questionnaire) to access the subject matter. The research survey was conducted with a number of students ($N=55$) in intermediate level speaking classes (Intensive English 2) at a university in Vietnam. Participants were given the questions and responded without writing down their names. The questions related to the real need of EFL students inquired which level they were at, what problems (pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary) they encountered in presenting speaking tasks, and what factors that affected their speaking performance.

4 RESULTS

For the first question, which asked, “Please indicate your level of English classified by your university”, participants chose their appropriate level: pre-intermediate (Intensive English 1 – IE1), intermediate (Intensive English 2 – IE2), and high intermediate (Academic English 1 – AE1). Then they were asked the second question: “What problem do you often have when presenting a speaking task?” as the choices were presented in table 1.

Table 1: Student’s problem in presenting a speaking task?

Problems	Vocabulary	Grammar	Pronunciation
No. of Sts			
IE 2	9	21	25

In Table 1, out of 55 participants, 25 (46%) said that the problem in their presenting speaking tasks was pronunciation; 21 students (38,2%) said the problem were related to grammar; and 9 students (16,4%) said that the problem was vocabulary.

For the third question: “Why do Vietnamese EFL students often drop English final sounds in pronouncing words?”, the choices of reasons were presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Reasons for dropping English final sounds in pronouncing words?

Reasons No. of Sts	Unimportant to pronounce the English final sounds correctly	The mistakes are not often corrected	Difficult to pronounce English final sounds
IE2	12	16	27

In Table 2, most students found it hard to pronounce the last sounds in English words with the agreement from 27 participants (49,1%); 16 students (29,1%) said the mistakes were not corrected; 12 students (21,8%) said it was unimportant pronounce the English final sounds correctly.

For the fourth question: “Which sound clusters do you find most difficult to pronounce?”, the choices for the clusters of sounds at the initial, middle and final positions were found in Table 3.

Table 3: Most difficult sound clusters found to pronounce

Sound clusters No. of Sts	Consonant clusters at the beginning of words like /str/ in <i>street</i>	Consonant clusters within and across words like /iksk/ in <i>excuse</i>	Consonant clusters at the end of words like /skt/ in <i>asked</i>
IE2	12	8	35

For this question, Table 3 indicated that 35 students (63,6%) focused on the consonant clusters at the end of words; 8 students (14,5%) said consonant clusters within and across words were difficult to pronounce: 12 students (21,8%) said consonant clusters at the beginning of words were difficult to pronounce.

For the fifth question: “What factor, in your opinion, can help you to do a speaking English task better?”, factors that contributed to further explaining students’ speaking performance were found in Table 4.

Table 4: Factors assisting students in performing a speaking English task better

Factors No. of Sts	Having ideas provided by teachers beforehand	Having ideas of your own	Having ideas of your own developed by teachers
IE2	19	8	28

As can be seen in table 4, 28 students (51 %) thought it easier for them to have ideas of their own developed by teachers. While 19 students (34,5 %) agreed that it was a good thing to develop a speaking based on their own ideas with teachers' help in expanding their ideas, 8 students (14,5 %) agreed to having ideas of their own.

For the sixth question: “What factor you think can affect your self-confidence in performing a speaking English task?”

Table 5: Factors affecting on students' self-confidence in performing a speaking English task

No. of Sts \ Factors	Being afraid of making mistakes	Peer pressure from group work or pair work	Not having a planned activity
IE2	18	11	26

It can be said from table 5 that out of 55 participants, 26 (47%) were not self-confident without having a planned activity; 11 students (20%) said that peer pressure from group work or pair work affected their self-confidence; 18 students (33%) said that they were afraid of making mistakes.

5 DISCUSSION

Through the investigation of 55 intermediate level students, most of them (46%) had the pronunciation problem, and 38,2% students said the problem was related to grammar as shown in Table 1. Tables 2 and 3 showed that 49,1% of them found it difficult to pronounce English final sounds and that 63,6% of them hardly pronounced consonant clusters at the end of words, respectively. Table 4 showed that 51% students needed teachers to help with expanding their own ideas. Table 5 showed 47% students needed to have a planned activity. Though the thought of fearing making mistakes hindered students from performing a speaking task well enough and the peer pressure from group work or pair work was a contributing factor, having a plan in advance still played a critical role in preparing students for speaking. Therefore, having a plan in advance, together with having ideas of students own developed by teachers can be of great help for students to communicate successfully.

These findings indicated that what prevented students from their presenting speaking tasks fall into the following categories:

- 1) Grammatical effect on students' performing speaking tasks.
- 2) Pronunciation of the single final sounds and the consonant clusters at the end of words.
- 3) Having a planned activity and ideas of students' own developed by teachers in doing speaking tasks.

The grammatical factor affecting Vietnamese EFL students' performance of speaking English results from the fact that Vietnamese is a non-inflectional while English is inflectional, which means that English consists of a lot of aspects related to the use of lexico-grammar (Cao, 1998 b).

As for the reasons why Vietnamese EFL students often have problems in pronouncing the final sounds and the consonant clusters at the end of words, Cao (1998 a) maintains that the common mistakes in pronunciation made by Vietnamese EFL students result from the lack of the linguistic knowledge of how the sounds are produced, and the mispronunciation is caused by mother tongue interference. Dropping final sounds is a common mistake made by Vietnamese students when they pronounce English words. They do not release many consonant sounds in the final position in English words. Consequently, when they say words such as *ask, sink, and white*, the native speakers of English will hear them sound like *as, sing, and why*.

As for the need of context of situation, ineffective verbal communication is supposed to result from inhibition, nothing to say, low participation, and mother-tongue (Ur, 1996). According to the survey, in doing speaking tasks, most students' problems due to that fact that they do not have ideas of students' own developed by teachers or do not have a plan in advance. These problems can be further explained by exploring what usually happen when students carry out speaking activities.

The following modified from the speaking activity design by Feez and Joyce (1998) can help EFL students improve their speaking ability.

- **Building the context**

Purpose of text (context of culture): Students have pictures for groups/oral presentations and discuss the purpose for doing this. Students identify, name and describe typical features of a place and express their feelings about them orally and with gestures, building initial vocabulary lists. The whole group discusses when and why they might want to talk about descriptions of the place.

What (field): Students sort vocabulary lists collected above into sets and check spellings, for instance, through excursions, research tasks about the place.

Who (tenor): Determine who the audience of such a text might be, their relationship to the author, their involvement with the topic (family, pen friend, classmates, teacher, other teachers and other friends. Represent the speaker/ listener relationship in a diagram. Build vocabulary sets of attitudinal words and phrases based on students' feelings about topic, use mind maps, select the items appropriate to the tenor.

How (mode): Consider the channel of communication (e.g. learner newspaper, diary, letter, poster, etc.) for this text-type (i.e. complex instructions, problematic exchange, casual conversation, information text, written discussion) and students choose one. Represent the distance in time and space between speaker and listener graphically.

- **Modeling**

Staging: Find or prepare a model description incorporating language features identified as significant in diagnostic analysis of learner text. Name stages and compare with other models of descriptions that students sequence in the text which has been cut up into stages, and sub-topics and label these. Students identify the descriptions from among a collection of different text-types.

Language features

Text unity: In groups and on PowerPoint with whole class, use a highlighter to join lexical strings and relate to stages/sub-topics, and use different highlighters to underline conjunctions and relate to stages, to link reference chains and relate to stages and to underline given information at the beginning of paragraphs and clauses and relate to stages. Develop cloze and substitution activities to focus on cohesive devices such as conjunctions (*and, also*), reference (*personal pronouns, there*). Develop matching and substitution activities antonyms, synonyms, “parts of” and “classes of” sets, etc. Cloze out and find substitutes for all the expressions of attitude and discuss different effects. Give students clauses to join with “*and*”.

Clause grammar: Students sequence jumbled groups and phrases into clauses noting different possibilities and their effects on meaning especially in relation to the order of information (i.e. given/theme and new information), compare with models. Develop cloze activities focusing on verb groups, noun groups, prepositional phrases of place.

Groups/words: Present parts of the noun group, verb group, prepositional phrases as required. Learners sequence jumbled words into groups. Cloze out parts of groups. Students collect examples of prepositional phrases, nominal groups, verbal groups. Remove some of one type of group, e.g. some noun groups, and learners read the text as if these were there (i.e. disappearing story).

- **Joint construction of the text**

Graphology: Integrate spelling activities into vocabulary building activities (look-cover-say, dictionary exercises, preparing personal dictionaries, sorting according to phonic and graphic clues etc.). Scaffold layout using outlined blocks and learners place sections of the text on appropriate block. Consider other graphic features as appropriate to channel and tenor, e.g. headings, illustrations, bold or highlighted words, underlining, block letters, and borders.

Act as prompts using PowerPoint or whiteboard while the class jointly constructs text, referring to the model. Draw learners’ attention to the stages of the speaking process, i.e. preparing to speak. Prepare skeleton texts with minimal clues and learners complete the text. Prepare information gap activities to construct the text. With the whole class, or in groups, edit a draft text, compare draft texts to the models. In groups learners prepare the texts to present to the whole class for discussion.

- **Independent construction of the text**

Through discussion, each student chooses a context and record a description (perhaps for homework). Students and/or teacher assess the recording, noting strengths, clarifying meanings and making suggestions for further improvement, e.g. in conferences, whole-class presentations using PowerPoint, peer discussion. Students edit and prepare final draft for presentation (e.g. model editing, and proofreading techniques as required). If students give oral description successfully on their own meeting all the performance criteria, they have achieved the competency. If not, this competency can be assessed in a later unit of work.

- **Linking related texts**

Compare and contrast oral written description with other text types (e.g. recount), comparing the purpose and the context, staging and language features. Alter one aspect of the context, e.g. topic, listener/speaker relationship, written/spoken forms, and ask learners to redraft their description. Alter the purpose of the text and ask learners to say it again (e.g. if description is being reviewed at the beginning of a class, instead of describing the situations, learners may have to imagine the situations.)

6 CONCLUSION

The findings based on the data analysis collected from the survey of students involved in the research showed that the greater percentage of students failed to perform speaking skill due to making grammar mistakes, mispronouncing final sounds, lacking teachers' development of their own ideas, or lacking a plan in advance in their way of communication. It can be seen that the mistakes in grammar or pronunciation are made because Vietnamese and English are two languages in different systems, and Vietnamese has neither sounds equivalent to English nor sounds pronounced in final position. It is necessary to help students recognize the English sounds, especially the final sounds, through identifying the similarities and differences between the sounds in English and the counterparts in Vietnamese, and thus improving their pronunciation.

It is of great concern for teachers of English that Vietnamese EFL students may not be able to communicate successfully. To effectively perform a language in any context of situations requires the great efforts of both teachers and learners, and best practices. This research was done is to identify students' problems if, based on the problem analysis, a newly designed speaking task could be useful to teach student to speak better. Such speaking problems as inhibition, nothing to say, low or uneven participation, mother-tongue use can be solved by the solution involved in the text-based syllabus design.

The study was conducted with intermediate level students at a university in Vietnam. However, it could pave the way for the proper collection and the choice of English language teaching resources for teachers to decide in order to meet the objective of the course after their students' problems were identified. The study may work as the basis for further solutions to these problems.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bailey, K. M., & Savage, L. (1994). *New Ways in Teaching Speaking*. New Ways in TESOL Series: Innovative Classroom Techniques. TESOL
- [2] Cao, H.X. (1998 a). *Âm vị học và tuyến tính*. Hà Nội: Nhà Xuất bản Đại học Quốc gia Hà Nội.
- [3] Cao, H.X. (1998 b). *Tiếng Việt – Mấy vấn đề ngữ âm, ngữ pháp, ngữ nghĩa*. TP HCM: Nhà Xuất bản Giáo dục.

- [4] Castillo, L. (1991). L2 Pronunciation Pedagogy: Where have we been? Where are we headed?. *The Language Teacher*, 14(10), 3-7.
- [5] Eggins, S. (1993). *An Introduction to Systemic Function Linguistics*. New York: Wellington House.
- [6] Feez, S. & Joyce, H. (1998). *Text-based Syllabus Design*. Sydney: Macquarie University.
- [7] Halliday, MAK & Matthiessen, C. MIM. (2004). *An Introduction to Functional Grammar*. London: Arnold.
- [8] Martin, J.R. (1992). *English Text – System and Structure*: Philadelphia: John Benjamin Publishing Company.
- [9] Morley, J. (1991). The pronunciation component in teaching English to speakers of other languages. *TESOL quarterly*, 25(3), 481-520.
- [10] Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2014). *Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching*. Cambridge university press.
- [11] Ur, P. (1996). *A Course in English teaching*. New York: Cambridge University Press